

**A HISTORICAL LANDMARK AND A SYMBOL OF RESPECT FOR THE ZARIA
TRADITIONAL INSTITUTION: KAFEN DAUDU
BY**

Muhammad Aminu Musa

Department of Architecture, Faculty of Environmental Design, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

ammusa@abu.edu.ng / mamzayopmo@gmail.com,

ORCID number: 0000-0003-4516-1281

Lawal Ahmed Tanimu

Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic Kaura-Namoda,

Zamfara State, Nigeria. babalawal82@gmail.com

Abstract

The tallest building in the Zazzau palace complex, *Kafen Daudu*, is a representation of both monarchy and power. The king and other guests can watch over celebrations or traditional religious events in front of Zazzau's palace from this 12-meter-tall pavilion. Many people said it started with a crazy man named Daudu, who used to sit in the sun at Zazzau's emir's palace and the monarch built him a shade. There was also the additional dimension that it came from a *jin* that periodically appeared in that location back in ancient times. According to some scholars, it came up from a single Galadima Daudu of habe origin under Sarki Abdullahi Burja's rule. An alternative viewpoint suggested that a building bore the name of one of Zaria's first emirs. The purpose of the study is to investigate *Kafen Daudu's* past as a Zazzau historical legacy. It was accomplished by examining the history of *Daudu* whose name was given to that building, and the changes it undergone over time. To investigate the history of *Kafen Daudu*, the historical strategy was combined with a qualitative research design and utilised an explorative design approach. Written and oral traditions were used to generate primary and secondary data. The findings indicated that it originated with Galadima Salmanu (I) when he was an acting monarch in the Zazzau emirate.

Keywords: Galadima, Kafen Daudu, Salmanu I, Zazzau

1.0 Introduction

Zaria was one of the greatest Hausa kingdoms of the 16th century, which was noted by Schwerdfeger, (2007) as the religious, political, and social centre of the then-Hausa kingdom. Its palace, which was constructed before colonisation, is the most important structure still standing in the city (Shema, Kiessel, & Atakara, 2023). The Palace is the most notable architectural structure in northern Nigeria and was built to represent the authority, presence, and identity of the traditional and royal institution inside the realm (Shema, Kiessel, & Atakara, 2023). One of

the major attractions among the various structures in Zazzau Palace presently is the *Kafen Daudu*. This structure not only enhances the palace's beauty but also holds a unique place in the palace's history and diverse activities. (Saidu, 2018). It is presently a pavilion where the emir sits and receives allegiance from his counselors during any traditional durbar. Thus, this structure expresses the power of the emir (Shema, Kiessel, & Atakara, 2023). It has received several changes, including being moved from its original location to its current location for a variety of reasons. It stands out in terms of scale, as the tallest part of the palace composition of about 12 metres height, compared with the general height of the palace (4–5 metres), and that of the entrance gate of about 7 metres tall (Nura, 2014). Its present form and proportion, with its symmetry, centre bulging volume, and arches, was influenced by the architectural remnants of the British colonial era as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Kafen Daudu* in its present form

Kafe is a Hausa name, which means stationed or firmly-founded and *Daudu* is a name of a person, therefore *Kafen Daudu* is a location where Daudu is consistently stationed or discovered. There are divergent views of the history of *Kafen Daudu*. For example, Alhaji Abubakar Ladan, a title holder of Chiroman Shantalin Zazzau and Chief Protocol Officer of the former emir of Zazzau HRH Alhaji Shehu Idris, noted that *Kafen Dauda* was the ancient gate of the palace and the *Daudu* was a traditional name given to the palace gatekeeper (Sa'idu, 2018). However, Idris (2020) revealed that *Kafen Daudu* originated from one Galadima Daudu of habe origin during the reign of Sarki Abdullahi Burja. This same idea was also the opinion of Abbas, Fagaci. Wakilin ayyukan Zazzau in an interview with him on Tuesday 2nd January 2024. However, a careful check of the literature revealed that the Galadima Daudu of habe origin was not in Zazzau but Kano as discussed by Giade, (2016) and Brady, (1978). Aliyu (2022) noted that it started with a crazy man named Daudu, who used to sit in the sun at Zazzau's emir's palace and the monarch built him a shade which is now known as *Kafen Daudu*. Pate (2022) opined that it

came from a *jin* which periodically appeared at that location in ancient times. An alternative viewpoint suggested that a building bore the name of one of Zaria's first emirs, Galadima Salmanu (I) (*Nwachukwu, 2004*). Therefore the study is aimed at investigating the history of *Kafen Daudu* as an architectural icon in Zazzau emirate and northern Nigeria in general. It is accomplished by examining the history of *Daudu* whose name was given to that building, and the changes it underwent over time.

2.0 Materials and Methods

In exploring the history of *Kafen Daudu* as a landmark and a symbol of respect for the Zaria traditional institution, oral sources, and local writings were given precedence to post-colonial writings due to their one-sided sources of information as evident in Government in Zazzau. This finding is similar to that of Abba (2005); Ezong and Nasidi, (2018); Adeleye, (1971); ABU school of History; as well as Ibadan School of History. To ensure checks and balances the oral sources were also checked using documented materials such as Annual reports of the year 1902 on the colonies of Northern Nigeria Number 409 by Lugard F.D.; Annual reports of the year 1903 on the colonies of Northern Nigeria Number 476 Lugard F.D; Revisionism and the historical interpretation of the Sokoto Caliphate by Ezong and Nasidi; From Caliphate to Federal Republic by Steve, P to mentioned a few. Others include unpublished works, especially PhD and MA theses were immensely utilized in the literature reviewed. They include History of Galadima Salmanu (I) by Musa Muazu; Usman Suleiman's M.A. thesis on the History of Birnin Zaria, 1350-1902; Hierarchy and Authority among the Hausa with Special Reference to the Period of the Sokoto Caliphate in the Nineteenth Century. Others are the Journal publications by Shema, Kiessel, and Atakara, (2023), Assessment of African Vernacular Built Environment and Power: The Case of the Walled City of Zaria, Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*; Raja. (2013). Architecture as a symbol of power, etc.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Results are presented based on the research objectives earlier raised in this paper.

3.1 Brief history of galadima salmanu the first.

Galadima Salmanu (I), was born in Zaria by Mallam Abubakar Mazadu Ahmad Usman who was a prominent Islamic scholar. Malam Ahmad came to Zaria in the company of Malam Abdulkarim one of the Emirs of Zazzau. The family of Malam Ahmad Usman were Fulani who came to Hausa land from Futa Jallo Senegal around 1800 AD (Abdurrahman, 1984) to propagate Islamic religion in the company of Fulani Islamic scholars, which include the ancestors of Sheikh Usman Danfodio. Malam Usman and his family lived shortly in Mani village of present Katsina state before proceeding to Katsina town where he became the chief Imam of Katsina

Friday mosque (Musa, 1991: Suleiman, 2007). During the jihad of Sheikh bn Fodio, Malam Ahmad together with Malam Abdulkarim (later became the emir of Zazzau) and their students went to Zaria for jihad (Suleiman, 2007). Malam Ahmad shortly died and left his son Abubakar in Zaria. Malam Abubakar like his father became a prominent Islamic scholar in Zaria and he was married to Fatima Karama the daughter of the emir of Zazzau Mamman Sani Ibn Yamusa. The emir had only two (2) daughters: - Fatima Karama and Fatima Babba, for his only son was killed in a battle. Fatima Babba was the grandmother of Waziri Isuhu of Unguwan juma Zaria (Alhaji Shehu Ahmed a title holder of Wakilin Tarihin Zazzau, 2024). Fatima Karama was the mother to Salmanu.

When Sambo became the emir of Zazzau in 1881 he deposed the then Sarkin Ruwa Yaji Abdullahi and appointed Salmanu (I) as *Sarkin ruwan Zazzau* (Smith, 1960) and also dismissed Galadima Adamu and appointed Salmanu (I) again to hold the two offices together (Smith, 1960: Musa, 1991: Wakilin Tarihi, 2024; Last, 1966: Sleiman, 2007; Idris, 2020). By tradition, any person who has the title of Galadima is also called *Daudu*. Salmanu (I) also held custody of the office of Makama Babba in the administration of Emir Sambo and superseded many other offices assigned by his principal (Shehu, 2010). He was also the Hakimin Birni (head of the capital city of Zazzaz) for a period of 24 years (1979-1903) (Last, 1966). When the emir Kwasau was removed in 1902, Galadima Salmanu (I) acted as the emir of Zazzau for nine (9) months 1902-1903 (Lugard, 1903: Sleiman, 2007; Kirk-Greene, 1972). Salmanu was also like his father and grandfather, an Islamic scholar and a business tycoon (Malam Inuwa, 2024, grand-son of Salmanu-I). He became very Powerful and popular in the entire emirate, especially the capital city (birni). That influenced his royal court song:

<i>Babba Galadima,</i>	Galadima the great,
<i>Babba Galadima,</i>	Galadima the great,
<i>Daudu Karfin birni,</i>	The Pillar of the Capital,
<i>Daudu rana da hazo</i>	In all circumstances, you are there,
<i>Zuciya taso Magana, baki yakasa fada,</i>	One wants to speak but his mouth can't.
<i>Agida babba a dawo babba,</i>	So powerful within and outside the city
<i>A yini zagin babba,</i>	Abuse him till dusk
<i>A kwana zagin babba,</i>	Abuse him till dawn
<i>Dole da safe ace babba ina kwana,</i>	But must be greeted in the morning,
<i>Gunu shama kosani</i>	The brave that withstands all rigours
<i>Chomo jiniyan gari</i>	Nightingale the siren of the town

Sarkin Busan Zazzau (2024) and Abdullahi, (2018)

His closeness to the emirs brought him many enemies across the ruling houses. These brought about some criticism and lies as well as propaganda against him. However, those did not distract him from focusing on his duty and the trust vested in him by his principals. That had prompted Lugard (1903) to praise him in the *Annual reports of the year 1902 on the colonies of Northern Nigeria Number 409*, where he was reported to have said, "Salmanu acted as an emir for nine (9)

months and proved an admirable ruler, thoroughly loyal and helpful to the resident”. Several errors were noted in the early writings of the post-colonial era, most importantly in Government in Zazzau of M.G. Smith (1960). H.F.C. Smith (1961) drew attention to some of the defects associated with the Government in Zazzau. He argued that the errors arose as a result of overreliance on defective sources and noted that such errors were capable of jeopardising the whole thesis. Those defective sources of the "Government in Zazzau" also affected Salmanu's personality. For example, M.G. Smith did not know the name of Galadima Salmanu (I) and kept calling him Suleimanu throughout his book. However, these two names are not the same, the meaning of "Salmanu" is "Safe" or "Secure" while that of "Sulayman" is "peace." Moreover, in the Fulani regime, there had never been any Galadima with the name Suleimanu in the history of Zazzau (Turbaning Ceremony of Galadiman Zazzau, 1996). Being the pioneer historian as noted by Sirajo, (2015), M.G. Smith was the pioneer author of the history of Zazzau whose book covered the pre-jihad period through the establishment of an emirate government and the imposition and consolidation of colonial rule to 1950, many researchers reported the same errors in their books against the Galadima Salmanu-I. They include Patton (1975); Hogben and Kirk-Green, (1966); Suleiman (2007); Adeleye (1972); Jamo, (2020), Sifawa, Sirajo, and Marafa, (2017) etc. Over-reliance on M.G. Smith's book made Jamo, (2020) not to notice the error in his paper on page 317 where he mentioned a descendent of Galadima Salmanu as "*Galadima Salmanu II.*"

Another propaganda of M.G. Smith was calling Galadima Salmanu (I) *habe*. That was also copied by many researchers without giving due consideration to what exactly he meant by "habe" as noted by Usman (2006). He questioned M.G. Smith's usage of "Habe, Hausa, and Fulani" and never defined any of them nor did he probe into their meaning and substance. Galadima Salmanu (I) was a Fulani man as reported in the introduction of this write-up and the evidence is all over him and his family. For example, his name "*Salamnu*" is mostly used by Fulani extraction, especially of Katsina origin, some of his children's and grandchildren's names are of Fulani origin such as "Hari, Nana, Sume, Fulani, Kako, Yero, Fendo, Makudu, Maude, Dije, Nagoggo to mentioned a few" (Musa, nd). All his descendants are looking Fulani up to today. His pictures and that of his immediate children are looking Fulani as indicated in Plate I-IX.

Plate I. Galadima Salmanu (I)

Plate II. Malam Sada Salmanu (I)

Plate III. Malam Nuhu Salmanu (I)

Plate IV. Alkali Jalalu Musa Salmanu (I)

Plate V. Malam Musa M Salmanu

Plate VI. Malam Inuwa A Salmanu

Plate VII. Galadima Salmanu II

Plate VIII. Galadima Nuhu Aliyu A. Salmanu (I)

Plate IX. Arc Nuhu S Mewada

The grandchildren were usually married within the family which was another Fulani practice. An in-depth discussion can be found in the “History of Galadima Salmanu (I)” for this is beyond the scope of this paper. Galadima Salmanu (I) had worked with four emirs of Zazzau: - Muhammadu Sambo; Yero; Kwasau; and Aliyu Dan Sidi. He was deposed and banished to Illorin in 1904 by the then emir of Zazzau Aliyu Dansidi (Sirajo, 2015; Hogben and Kirk-Green, 1966; Adeleye, 1972: M.G. Smith, 1960). He was accused of intriguing against the emir’s Authority (Sirajo, 2015). However, he was pardoned later but could not come back due to his terminal illness (Wakilin Tarihi, 2024) and was buried in Ilorin by the side of the Illorin emir’s palace.

3.2. *Kafen daudu*

When the emir Kwasau was removed in 1902, the Galadima Salmanu (I) acted as an interim emir for nine (9) months (Lugard 1904: Sifawa, Sirajo, and Marafa, 2017) in charge of the affairs of the Zazzau emirate (Kirk-Greene, 1972: Smith, 1960). So instead of him to use the emir’s chambers in Zazzau’s palace, he built a temporary shade in front of the emir’s palace where he discharged his duty as an interim emir of Zazzau. This was a sign of respect for the traditional institution of Zazzau since he was not a substantive emir. Moreover, because he was so punctual

in his duty and always there for his people, the people of Zazzau started calling it *Kafen Daudu* (Malam Inuwa 2024, a grandson of Salmanu I). It was attached to the main entrance of the palace as shown in Plate X. Residents of Zazzau eventually began referring to the entire entry construction as *Kafen Daudu* gate. One of the evidence was found on the cover page of the

Kafen Daudu
Friday mosque

Kafen Daudu

Plate X. Zaria Emir's place in 1906

installation pamphlet of the 18th emir of Zazzau in 1975 when the whole main entrance was named *Kafen Daudu*, as shown in Plate XI.

Main Entrance of the Emir's Palace
(*Kafen Daudu*).

Plate XI. Installation pamphlet of the 18th emir of Zazzau named *Kafen Daudu*

A new gate with a central arch was installed during Sarkin Ibrahim's rule (1924–1936). The archway allowed vehicles and horses to pass through, and an open entryway on the right side was used by pedestrians (*Kafen Daudu*) (Shema, Kiessel, & Atakara, 2023). The space to the left of the arch was utilised as an Islamic school, and the thickness of the gate allowed it to function as a structure (DeVito, 2019) as indicated in Plate XII.

Plate XII. *Kafen Daudu* with central arc and Islamic class

More adornments and modifications to the entryway were mandated by the two subsequent Emirs, Ja'afaru (r. 1936–1959) and Mohammadu Aminu (1959–1975). The pattern grew more complex and smaller during Sarkin Mohammadu Aminu's rule (DeVito, 2019). By 1963, colour had been added to these reliefs as shown in Plate XIII.

Plate XIII. Emperor's palace during Mohammad Aminu

Plate XIV. Emir's palace in 1995

In 1982, Emir Shehu Idris built a new gate in place of the previous one as indicated in Plate xiv. The remodeling, which eschewed mud construction, was overseen by Alhaji Haruna, Zaria's master builder at the time and a descendant of Mallam Mikaila, the architect of the Zaria mosque (DeVito, 2019). A concrete frame and cement blocks made up the new building components. Specially prepared mud was mixed with cement. The late Galadiman Zazzau Alhaji Salmanu (II)

Giwa persuaded the 18th emir of Zazzau to take into consideration resurrecting the historical heritage of Kafen Daudu in 1995, when the palace was to be maintained by the Kaduna State Government. The emir accepted the request and moved the original location to the right side of the 17th emir's chamber as a pavilion. The Galadima Salmanu (II) funded its construction as a pavilion (malam Inuwa, 2024) as indicated in Plate xv-xvi.

Plate XV. Zazzau Emis Palace under construction of a new *Kafen Daudu* in 1995

Plate XVI Zazzau Emis palace with new *Kafen Daudu* in 1995

Plate XVII. Emirs palace in 1995

From 2010 to 2011 another renovation of the Zaria emir's palace came up again and the 18th emir of Zazzau Alhaji Dr. Shehu Idris extended the *Kafen Daudu* to cover up the upper part of Muhammad Aminu Chamber and its side space as shown in Plate xviii.

Plate XVIII. Zazzau Emis palace with new *Kafen Daudu* in 2011 to date.

5.0 Conclusion

The study has concluded that *Kafen Daudu* originated from a temporary shed of the late Galadima Salmanu (I) when he was an acting emir of Zazzau in 1902 and it was attached to the main entrance of the palace. The present position of *Kafen Daudu* is its 3rd position historically and all were to preserve the historical heritage of the landmark and a symbol of respect to the Zaria traditional institution. Moreover, the scale and proportion of the *Kafen Daudu* are linked to the expression of power, dominance, intimidation, and authority.

References

- Abba A. (2005). Tribute to Dr. Yusuf Bala Usman. *Leadership Nigerian Newspaper*, 3-4.
- Abbas, Fagaci, Wakilin ayyukan Zazzau (2024: January 2) Oral Interview Conducted by the Researcher at Zaria city.
- Abdullahi, R. (2018). .An Analysis of Selected Royal Court Songs of Zazzau Emirate. Unpublished MA Thesis, Department of English and Literary Studies, Faculty of Arts, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria
- Abdurrahman, I, D. (1984). *Islam in Nigeria*. Gaskiya Corporation Zaria.
- Adeleye, R. A. (1971). *Power and Diplomacy in Northern Nigeria*. London, Longman
- Adeleye, R. A. (1972). Power and Diplomacy in Northern Nigeria 1804–1906: the Sokoto Caliphate and its Enemies. *Africa*, 42(4), 353–353. doi:10.2307/115851
- Alhaji Shehu Ahmed a title holder of Wakilin Tarihin Zazzau,(2024). Oral Interview Conducted by the Researcher at Zaria city.
- Aliyu, M.M. (2022). Ko akwai Wanda zai iya bamu takaitaccen tarihin, Kafen Daudu? *Kasar Zazzau a Jiya Da Yau*. Retrieved from https://web.facebook.com/kasarzazzauajiyadayau/photos/a.999576543399713/5810566728967313/?type=3&_rdc=1&_rdr
- Brady, R. P. (1978). Hierarchy and authority among the Hausa with special reference to the period of the Sokoto Caliphate in the nineteenth century [PhD thesis]. University of Oxford.
- DeVito M (2019) Gate to the Emir's palace, Zaria; Hausa cultural proclamation. Cleveland State University. <https://access.thebrightcontinent.org/items/show/20> (10 October 2019).
- Ezonbi, B & Nasidi, A.N. (2018). Revisionism and the Historical Interpretation of the Sokoto Caliphate: The writings of Murray. *A Journal of Humanities*, 14, 44-49.
- Giade, A.A. (2016). *An archaeological investigation in Shira region, Bauchi, northeast Nigeria*. An unpublished PhD Thesis, Norwich School of Art, Media and American Studies (AMA), University of East Anglia.
- Idris A. J. (2020). Life time of galadima (salihu) dokaje of the zazzau emirate: an implication to

- administration and public policy. *Lapai International Journal of Administration LIJAD*, 3(3), P 311
- Kirk-Greene, A.H.M.(1972). *Gazetters of Northern Provinces of Nigeria-Volume I- The (Bauchi, Sokoto, Zaria, Kano). Frak class; London.*
- Last, D. M. (1966). A solution to the problems of dynastic chronology in 19th century zaria and kano. *Journal of the Historical Society of Nigeria*, 3(3), 461–469.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/41856707>
- Lugard F.D. (1903). *Annual reports of the year 1902 on the colonies of Northern Nigeria* Number 409 . Darling & son Ltd,UK.
- Lugard F.D. (1904). *Annual reports of the year 1903 on the colonies of Northern Nigeria* Number 476 . Darling & son Ltd,UK.
- Malam Inuwa, grand-son of Salmanu (I) (2024 january 15th). Oral Interview Conducted by the Researcher at Zaria city
- Musa M.(nd). *History of Galadima Salmanu I. Unpublished*
- Nura, J. (2014). Traditional Hausa architecture in the royal palace, city walls. In: Deubel TF, Tissières H and Youngstedt SM (eds) *Saharan Crossroads: Exploring Historical, Cultural, and Artistic Linkages between North and West Africa*, p.235.
- Nwachukwu, M.P. (2004). *Nigeria: Art & Book Review: Memories of Artists Cnfab in Zaria 2003. VANGUARD News paper Nigeria, 2004. Retrieved from*
<https://allafrica.com/stories/200401080615.html>
- Pate, M. (2022). Ko akwai Wanda zai iya bamu tafaitaccen tarihin, Kafen Daudu?
Kasar Zazzau a Jiya Da Yau. Retrieved from
https://web.facebook.com/kasarzazzauajiyadayau/photos/a.999576543399713/5810566728967313/?type=3&_rdc=1&_rdr
- Raja T. (2013). Architecture as a symbol of power. Retrieved from
<https://www.slideshare.net/Tousifra1/architecture-as-a-symbol-of-power>
- Sa'idu, I. (2018). Zaria palace decoration symbolises tradition, royalty. DAILY Trust Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://dailytrust.com/zaria-palace-decoration-symbolises-tradition-royalty-266469/>
- Sarkin Busan Zazzau (2024 January, 5th). Oral Interview Conducted by the Researcher at Zaria city
- Schwerdtfeger, F.W. (2007). *Hausa Urban Art and Its Social Background: External House Decorations in a Northern Nigerian City (Vol.6)*. Münster: LIT Verlag.
- Shehu, S (2010). *The Sokoto Factors in the Politics of Zazzau C.1804-1903*. Department of History, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria
- Shema, A. I., Kiessel, M., & Atakara, C. (2023). Assessment of African Vernacular Built Environment and Power: The Case of the Walled City of Zaria, Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219096231197742>
- Shea, P. J. (2003). Book Review: M. G. Smith, *Government in Kano 1350-1950 in Kano Studies: A Journal of Savanna and Sudanic Research*, 1(2), p. 147
- Sifawa, A.A, Sirajo, M.S. & Marafa, M. (2017). Revisiting the Budgetary Deficit Factor in the 1914 Amalgamation of Northern and Southern Protectorates: A Case Study of Zaria Province, 1903-1914. *International Journal of Liberal Arts and Social Science*, 5(9), 1-16

- Sirajo, H. (2015). A History of District and Local Government Administration in the Northern Districts of Zazzau Emirate, C. 1902 – 1976. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Department of History, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Smith, H. F. C. (1962). The Dynastic Chronology of Fulani Zaria. *Journal of the Historical Society of Nigeria*, 2(2), Ibadan, University Press, p. 278.
- Smith, M. G. (Michael G. (1960). *Government in Zazzau 1800-1950*. Published for the International African Institute by Oxford University Press. <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ms12-015>
- Steve (2016). A tale of two emirs in Colonialism and Bureaucratizing Emirates, 1900–1948. Duke University Press. page 38-39 <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822374541-002>
- Suleiman, U. (2007). A history of birnin zaria from 1350 – 1902. Unpublished MA Thesis. History Department, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Usman, Y. B. (2006). The Problem of Ethnic Categories in the Study of the Historical Development of Central Sudan: A Critique of M. G. Smith and Others. *In Beyond Fairy Tales*, Vol. 1, CERDDERT, Zaria. pp.2.
- Wakilin Tarihin Zazzau,(2024). Oral Interview conducted by the Researcher at Zaria city.